

Research article

Without human cytomegalovirus infection, no essential hypertension

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Abstract:

Background:

To our knowledge, no study has provided strict evidence of a clear relationship between a human cytomegalovirus infection and human essential hypertension.

Methods:

To examine the possible role of human cytomegalovirus infection in the aetiology of essential hypertension, a literature searched through the electronic database PubMed was performed. Data were accurately assessed and reanalysed by new statistical methods.

Results:

The meta-analysis results of this study provide evidence that human cytomegalovirus infection and essential hypertension are connected.

Conclusion:

The hypothesis without human cytomegalovirus infection, no essential hypertension appears to be true.

Keywords: Human cytomegalovirus; Essential hypertension; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k

1. Introduction

Hypertension has been defined in the year 1999 by WHO/ISH Hypertension Guidelines (see [Who, 1999](#)) as systolic blood pressure (SBP) ≥ 140 mmHg (18.7 kPa) and/or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) ≥ 90 mmHg (12.0 kPa). Unfortunately, the cause or a precise cause of essential hypertension (EH) is unknown. To date, hypertension is understood as a disease which is caused by a combination of various environmental and genetic factors (see [Kunes and Zicha, 2009](#)), an effective early prevention for this

disease is not available. In contrast to risk factor theories of hypertension, emerging evidence indicates that infectious agents like the human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) might be related to hypertension (see [Feng and Yuan, 2001](#); [Cheng et al., 2009](#); [Haarala et al., 2012](#); [Vahdat et al., 2013](#); [Cao et al., 2014](#); [Tang et al., 2014](#); [Jeong et al., 2016](#); [Firth et al., 2016](#); [Hui et al., 2016](#); [Lv et al., 2017](#); [Feng et al., 2018](#)) too.

Human cytomegalovirus (see [Dolan et al., 2004](#); [Cunningham et al., 2010](#)) is a large (see [Stern-Ginossar et al., 2012](#)) double-stranded deoxy nucleic acid (dsDNA) virus (see [Sanger et al., 1977](#)) belonging to the beta-herpes virus family (see [Dolan et al., 2004](#)) which is ranked among one of the most common infections in adults globally (see [Bate et al., 2010](#)) with the seropositive rates ranging from 60–99% (see [Cannon et al., 2010](#)). Once acquired, HCMV establishes lifelong latency (see [Crough and Khanna, 2009](#)) and may periodically reactivate without causing symptoms in healthy individuals. Theoretically, a common widespread virus, such as HCMV , might be related to hypertension too. In mice, Cheng et al. (see [Cheng et al., 2009](#)) found that mouse cytomegalovirus infection caused a significant **increase of blood pressure independent of a high cholesterol diet**. Previous research documented repeatedly that HCMV seropositivity (see [Firth et al., 2016](#)) is associated with hypertension (see [Li et al., 2011](#)). Meanwhile, various studies are reporting that HCMV is related somehow with hypertension (see [Hui et al., 2016](#)). Moreover, studies found that HCMV IgG titers are associated with high blood pressure (see [Haarala et al., 2012](#); [Jeong et al., 2016](#); [Tang et al., 2014](#); [Li et al., 2017](#)). In other words, the conviction is solidifying more and more that HCMV plays an important part in the pathogenesis of essential hypertension. In this context, HCMV immunoglobulin G (IgG) titers may represent indirectly the cumulative HCMV burden while HCMV itself remains in the human host throughout lifetime (see [Sinclair and Sissons, 2006](#)). Reactivation of latent HCMV infection might result in HCMV IgG changes and on the long run in higher HCMV IgG antibody concentrations. In point of fact, most of the aforementioned studies demonstrated a positive relationship between HCMV infection and hypertension, but the cause of essential hypertension is still not identified. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to comprehensively report on the causal relationship between HCMV IgG titers and essential hypertension.

2. Material and methods

HCMV is a double-stranded DNA virus of the β -herpesvirus family genome and persists in certain human host cells for life after primary infection (see [Dolan et al., 2004](#)), HCMV is never cleared by the human host. Reactivation and latency are defining characteristics of HCMV infection. A reactivation from latency (see [Sinclair and Sissons, 2006](#)) even in non-immunocompromised individuals can result in serious disease. HCMV IgG indicates HCMV positivity or latency, while changes of HCMV IgG during HCMV latency (see [Mehta et al., 2000](#)) might point to recent or frequent HCMV reactivation. Reactivations or superinfections may result in higher titers of HCMV immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies, but of increased levels of pro-inflammatory markers too. HCMV -specific IgG is used as an indicator for long-term HCMV infection. HCMV IgG titers are measured while using different kits. The cutoff value for HCMV positivity varies from study to study. The sensitivity and specificity of these kits is different, which might have negative impact on the results achieved.

2.1. Material

2.1.1. Literature search

A search for relevant studies has been performed until August 18, 2021 using the potential of the electronic database PubMed with the following keywords used not individually but in combination: “cytomegalovirus” and “essential hypertension”. Reporting follows in adherence to Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (see [Moher et al., 2009](#); [Liberati et al., 2009](#)).

Table 1. *Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis*

Identification:	PubMed	30
Screening:	Articles excluded I	19
Eligibility:	Articles eligible for analysis	11
	Articles excluded II	2
Inclusion:	Studies included (meta-analysis)	9

2.1.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies in English language which investigated the relationship between HCMV and EH were considered. Unfortunately, the study of Feng et al. (see [Feng and Yuan, 2001](#)) and of Cheng et al. (see [Cheng et al., 2009](#)) could not be taken into account. The presentation of the data by Haarala et al. (see [Haarala et al., 2012](#)) has been inappropriate.

Reviews, case reports, letters, conference abstracts, or expert opinions were excluded and not considered.

2.1.3. Study selection and characteristics

The literature search yielded 30 potentially eligible titles. The abstracts were reviewed, inappropriate articles were excluded and removed. At the end, 9 articles which met the inclusion criteria and were eligible for meta-analyses.

2.1.4. Data extraction and assessment of study quality

The data from articles which met which the inclusion and exclusion criteria were extracted and statistically analysed.

2.1.5. CMV IgG and Smoking

Li et al. (see study of [Li et al., 2017](#)) documented the seroprevalence of HCMV IgG in the Han Chinese population as $(547/563)*100 = 97.16\%$. In particular circumstances, it may be that there is a relationship between a HCMV infection and the consumption of nicotine? As a result, a nicotine consumption might help to get a HCMV infection under control. Li et al. (see study of [Li et al., 2017](#)) analysed the relationship between an infection with human cytomegalovirus and smoking (see table 2) and provided the following data on this relationship.

Table 2. CMV IgG and Smoking (Study Li et al. , 2017).

		Smoking		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	192	355	547
	NO	5	11	16
		197	366	563
Causal relationship $k = 0,0134153680$				
p Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,4895030843				
p (SINE) = 0,9911190053				
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,1269				
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 1,5625				
p Value (SINE) = 0,0088416751				
OR = 0,3606				
RR (nc) = 1,1232				
RR (sc) = 1,0048				
IOR = 1,1899				
p(IOI)= 0,621669627				
p(IOU)= 0,321492007				

The study design of the study of has been unfair ($p(\text{IOU}) = +0,321492007$; see table 2). Li et al. (see study of [Li et al., 2017](#)) were able to provide evidence (see table 2) that a HCMV infection is a necessary condition of smoking ($p(\text{SINE})=0,9911190053$; $p(\text{Value (SINE)})=0,0088416751$) while the causal relationship k is positive. In other words, **without a HCMV infection, no smoking**.

2.1.6. CMV IgG and alcohol - unfair

Does alcohol exhibit properties, which, depending upon circumstances, brings a HCMV infection of humans under their control? The relationship between a HCMV infection and the consumption of alcohol has been investigated by Li et al. (see study of [Li et al., 2017](#)) who provided the following data on this relationship.

Table 3. CMV IgG and Alcohol (Study Li et al. , 2017; Unfair study design).

		Alcohol		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	135	412	547
	NO	4	12	16
		139	424	563
Causal relationship k =		-0,0012328608		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		0,6423341892		
p (SINE) =		0,9928952043		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) =		0,1151		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) =		1,0000		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0070796163		
OR =		0,2611		
RR (nc) =		0,9872		
RR (sc) =		0,9995		
IOR =		0,9830		
p(IOI)=		0,724689165		
p(IOU)=		0,218472469		

As can be seen (see table 3), the study design has been a little unfair. An incorrect control group (no alcohol consumption) lead to contradictory results ($k < 0$) while significant conditio sine qua non relationship.

2.1.7. CMV IgG and alcohol - fair

Table 4 presents data of the study of Li et al. (see study of Li et al., 2017) with a fictive control group of 139 newborn children, of whom 4 were HCMV positive, while none of these newborn children consumed alcohol.

Table 4. CMV IgG and Alcohol (Study Li et al. , 2017; Fair study design).

		Alcohol		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	135	4	139
	NO	4	135	139
		139	139	278
Causal relationship k =		0,9424460432		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		0,0000000000		
p (SINE) =		0,9856115108		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B _t) =		0,1151		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A _t) =		0,1151		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0142854696		
OR =		0,9712		
RR (nc) =		33,7500		
RR (sc) =		33,7500		
IOR =		1.139,0625		
p(IOI)=		0		
p(IOU)=		0		

The data and the statistical results, based on a fictive control group, are presented by table 4.

2.1.8. The study of Li et al., 2011

Li et al. (see [Li et al., 2011](#)) investigated the plasma from 194 patients and from 97 controls and found decreased HCMV virus titer in control subjects compared with hypertensive patients.

Table 5. CMV IgG and Hypertension (Study Li et al., 2011; Unfair study design).

		Hypertension		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	183	90	273
	NO	11	7	18
		194	97	291
Causal relationship k =		+0,0302613766		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		0,3893482895		
p (SINE) =		0,9621993127		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) =		0,6237		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) =		6,7222		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0370951591		
OR =		0,6529		
RR (nc) =		1,0969		
RR (sc) =		1,0167		
IOR =		0,0055		
p(IOI) =		0,271477663		
p(IOU) =		0,604810997		

Li et al., 2011 analysed the relationship between an infection by human cytomegalovirus (as indicated by HCMV IgG) and hypertension (see table 5). However, their study design has been unfair (p(IOU)= +0,604810997).

2.1.9. The study of Li et al., 2012

Li et al. (see [Li et al., 2012](#)) published data of 6303 participants aged 16–49 years in NHANES 1999–2002, 3975 had HCMV infection and 939 had hypertension.

Table 6. CMV IgG and Hypertension (Study Li et al. , 2012).

		Hypertension		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	539	3436	3975
	NO	400	1928	2328
		939	5364	6303
Causal relationship k =		-0,0490995079		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		0,9999532107		
p (SINE) =		0,9365381564		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) =		170,3940		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) =		68,7285		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0614900712		
OR =		0,3914		
RR (nc) =		0,7892		
RR (sc) =		0,8961		
IOR =		-0,0898		
p(IOI)=		0,481675393		
p(IOU)=		0,220371252		

However, the data of Li et al. (see [Li et al., 2012](#)) are more or less self-contradictory ($k < 0$) and have not been considered for further discussion.

2.1.10. The study of Vahdat et al., 2013

The prevalence of IgG antibodies against HCMV in the hypertensive group compared to healthy persons has been investigated by Vahdat et al.(see study of [Vahdat et al., 2013](#)).

Table 7. CMV IgG and Hypertension (Study Vahdat et al. , 2013).

		Hypertension		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	441	1192	1633
	NO	18	103	121
		459	1295	1754
Causal relationship k =		0,0699337266		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		0,0015605331		
p (SINE) =		0,9897377423		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) =		0,7059		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) =		2,6777		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0102097804		
OR =		0,3101		
RR (nc) =		1,8154		
RR (sc) =		1,0438		
IOR =		2,1170		
p(IOI)=		0,669327252		
p(IOU)=		0,192702395		

Even the study design of Vahdat et al.(see study of [Vahdat et al., 2013](#)) has been unfair.

2.1.11. The study of Tang et al., 2014

Tang et al. (see study of [Tang et al., 2014](#)) investigated the relationship between human cytomegalovirus infection and essential hypertension in Kazakh and Han Chinese populations. Among the 467 hypertensive Kazakh participants, 452 Kazakhs had HCMV infection (96.8%). The prevalence of HCMV infection in hypertensive participants in the study cohort of the study of Tang et al. (see study of [Tang et al., 2014](#)) was high.

Table 8. CMV IgG and Hypertension (Study Tang et al. , 2014; Unfair study design).

		Hypertension		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	452	310	762
	NO	15	23	38
		467	333	800
Causal relationship k =		+0,0856279961		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		0,0126382451		
p (SINE) =		0,9812500000		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B _t) =		0,4818		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A _t) =		5,9211		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0185753123		
OR =		0,5938		
RR (nc) =		1,5027		
RR (sc) =		1,0397		
IOR =		0,0161		
p(IOI)=		0,36875		
p(IOU)=		0,53625		

The study design with p(IOU)=0,53625 has been unfair. The 452 HCMV positive from 467 hypertensive Kazakh participants can be compared with a fictive control group of 15 HCMV positive out of 467 newborn children.

2.1.12. The study of Jeong et al., 2016

Jeong et al. (see study of [Jeong et al., 2016](#)) investigated the relationship between HCMV antibody levels and systolic blood pressure levels. The data provided by Jeong et al. (see study of [Jeong et al., 2016](#)) are presented by table 9.

Table 9. CMV IgG and Hypertension (Study Jeong et al., 2016; Unfair study design).

		Hypertension		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	81	22	103
	NO	0	0	0
		81	22	103
Causal relationship k =		-		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		1,0000000000		
p (SINE) =		1,0000000000		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B _t) =		0,0000		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A _t) =		-		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0000000000		
OR =		0,7864		
RR (nc) =		-		
RR (sc) =		1,0000		
IOR =		0		
p(IOI)=		0,213592233		
p(IOU)=		0,786407767		

2.1.13. The study of Li et al., 2017

Li et al. (see study of [Li et al., 2017](#)) investigated the relationship between human cytomegalovirus and the pathogenesis of increased arterial blood pressure.

Table 10. CMV IgG and Hypertension (Study Li et al. , 2017).

		Hypertension		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	361	186	547
	NO	11	5	16
		372	191	563
Causal relationship k =		-0,0096644075		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		0,6820656188		
p (SINE) =		0,9804618117		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) =		0,3253		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) =		7,5625		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0193485549		
OR =		0,6501		
RR (nc) =		0,9599		
RR (sc) =		0,9965		
IOR =		-0,0012		
p(IOI)=		0,310834813		
p(IOU)=		0,632326821		

2.1.14. The study of Feng et al., 2018

Feng et al. (see [Feng et al., 2018](#)) published data which indicate that HCMV may contribute to hypertension.

Table 11. CMV IgG and Hypertension (Study Feng et al. , 2018).

		Hypertension		
		YES	NO	
CMV IgG	YES	348	336	684
	NO	12	24	36
		360	360	720
Causal relationship k =		0,0764719113		
p Value right tailed (HGD) =		0,0293021407		
p (SINE) =		0,9833333333		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) =		0,4000		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) =		4,0000		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0165285462		
OR =		0,5167		
RR (nc) =		1,5263		
RR (sc) =		1,0357		
IOR =		0,0175		
p(IOI)=		0,45		
p(IOU)=		0,45		

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Independence

Definition 2.1 (Independence).

Let $p(A_t)$ denote the single probability of an event A_t at the (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t . Let $p(B_t)$ denote the single probability of an event B_t at the same (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t . Let $p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability of both events, $A_t \wedge B_t$ at the same (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t . Mathematically, the independence of both [Moivre \(1718\)](#); [Kolmogoroff \(1950\)](#) events $A_t \wedge B_t$ at the same (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t in terms of probability theory is defined as

$$p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \quad (2.1)$$

2.2.2. Random variables and two by two tables

The relationship between random variables [Gosset \(1914\)](#) can be investigated by different [Gosset \(1908\)](#) methods, including the tools of probability theory, too. The theoretical distribution of two Bernoulli random variables is illustrated by table 12.

Definition 2.2 (Bernoulli random variables and a two by two table).

Table 12. The theoretical distribution of two Bernoulli random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	A_t	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

There are conceivable conditions under which *the probability of an event, an outcome, a success et cetera is constant from Bernoulli trial $Uspensky (1937)$ to Bernoulli trial t* . Under these circumstances, it is

$$A \equiv E(A) \equiv N \times p(A_t) \quad (2.2)$$

and

$$B \equiv E(B) \equiv N \times p(B_t) \quad (2.3)$$

and

$$a \equiv E(A \wedge B) \equiv N \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \quad (2.4)$$

where $a, b, c, d, A, \underline{A}, B, \underline{B}$ denote the expectation values. In general, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} A &= a + b \\ &\equiv N - \underline{A} \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

and that

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{A} &= c + d \\ &\equiv N - A \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$\begin{aligned} B &= a + c \\ &\equiv N - \underline{B} \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

and equally

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{B} &= b + d \\ &\equiv N - B \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

and

$$a + b + c + d \equiv A + \underline{A} \equiv B + \underline{B} \equiv N \quad (2.9)$$

Historically, Karl Pearson (1857-1936) has been the first to introduce in 1904 [Pearson \(1904\)](#) the two by two or contingency table between two binomial random variables, which is illustrated by table [13](#).

Table 13. Binomial random variables and a two by two table

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	d
		B	\underline{B}	N

2.2.3. Necessary condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]

Definition 2.3 (Necessary condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

There are circumstances between events where **without** the occurrence of an event A_t **no** occurrence of an event B_t . In other words, the occurrence of an event A_t is a necessary condition for the occurrence of another event B_t . Mathematically, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić (2011), Barukčić (1989), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (2005), Barukčić (2017a), Barukčić (2017b), Barukčić (2019a), Barukčić (2020a), Barukčić (2016a), Barukčić (2018), Barukčić (2016b), Barukčić (2017c), Barukčić (2020b), Barukčić (2021), Barukčić (2019b)) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

In general, it is $p(A_t < B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ (see Table 14).

Table 14. The theoretical distribution of a necessary condition

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	A_t	FALSE	+0	$p(d_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

2.2.4. Sufficient condition [*Conditio per quam*]

Definition 2.4 (Sufficient condition [*Conditio per quam*]).

Conditions, where the occurrence of an event A_t is accompanied by the occurrence of another event B_t need to be considered to. The sufficient ($A_t \rightarrow B_t$) condition relationship or **if** the occurrence of an event A_t **then** occurrence of an event B_t , denoted by $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić (2011), Barukčić (1989), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (2005), Barukčić (2017a), Barukčić (2017b), Barukčić (2019a), Barukčić (2020a), Barukčić (2016a), Barukčić (2018), Barukčić (2016b), Barukčić (2017c), Barukčić (2020b), Barukčić (2021), Barukčić (2019b)) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t)}{N \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.11}$$

Furthermore, it is $p(A_t \succ B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 15).

Table 15. The theoretical distribution of a sufficient condition

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

2.2.5. Causal relationship k

Definition 2.5 (Causal relationship k).

Let $p(U_t)$ denote the single probability of an event U_t (German: Ursache, a cause) at the (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t . Let $\sigma(U_t)$ denote the standard deviation of a cause U_t at the (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t . Let $p(W_t)$ denote the single probability of an event W_t (German: Wirkung, an effect) at the same (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t . Let $\sigma(W_t)$ denote the standard deviation of an effect W_t at the (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t . Let $p(U_t \wedge W_t)$ denote the joint probability of both events, $U_t \wedge W_t$ at the same (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t . Let $\sigma(U_t, W_t)$ denote the co-variance between a cause U_t and an effect W_t at every single Bernoulli trial t . The cause-effect relationship k (Barukčić (2011), Barukčić (1989), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (2005), Barukčić (2017a), Barukčić (2017b), Barukčić (2019a), Barukčić (2020a), Barukčić (2016a), Barukčić (2018), Barukčić (2016b), Barukčić (2017c), Barukčić (2020b), Barukčić (2021), Barukčić (2019b)) between

a cause U_t (German: Ursache) and an effect W_t (German: Wirkung) is defined at each single Bernoulli trial t in terms of statistics and probability theory as

$$k(U_t, W_t) \equiv \frac{\sigma(U_t, W_t)}{\sigma(U_t) \times \sigma(W_t)} \quad (2.12)$$

$$\equiv \frac{p(U_t \wedge W_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t))) \times (p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t)))}}$$

2.2.6. Study design and bias

Definition 2.6 (Study design and bias).

A study design should be fair (see Barukčić, 2019c,d) and representative as much as possible in order to assured data, which can be worked with. The index of unfairness (see Barukčić, 2019c) and the index of independence (see Barukčić, 2019d) are indicating to which extent data could be biased. Under ideal conditions, it is desirable that $p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI})$.

Table 16. The quality of data (see Barukčić, 2019c, p. 25)

$p(\text{IOU})$	Quality of study design
$0 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,25$	Unfair study design
$0,25 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,5$	Very unfair study design
$0,5 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,75$	Highly unfair study design
$0,75 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 1,0$	Extremely unfair study design

2.3. Statistical methods

The necessary (Barukčić (2011), Barukčić (1989), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (2005), Barukčić (2017a), Barukčić (2017b), Barukčić (2019a), Barukčić (2020a), Barukčić (2016a), Barukčić (2018), Barukčić (2016b), Barukčić (2017c), Barukčić (2020b), Barukčić (2021), Barukčić (2019b)) condition relationship, the sufficient (Barukčić (2011), Barukčić (1989), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (2005), Barukčić (2017a), Barukčić (2017b), Barukčić (2019a), Barukčić (2020a), Barukčić (2016a), Barukčić (2018), Barukčić (2016b), Barukčić (2017c), Barukčić (2020b), Barukčić (2021), Barukčić (2019b)) condition relationship and the causal relationship k (Barukčić (2011), Barukčić (1989), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (1997), Barukčić (2005), Barukčić (2017a), Barukčić (2017b), Barukčić (2019a), Barukčić (2020a), Barukčić (2016a), Barukčić (2018), Barukčić (2016b), Barukčić (2017c), Barukčić (2020b), Barukčić (2021), Barukčić (2019b)) were used to evaluate the possible causal relationship between B19 and AML. The index of independence (see Barukčić, 2019d) (IOI) and the index of unfairness (see Barukčić, 2019c) (IOU) was used to evaluate the methodological quality of the data of the study included. The chi-square goodness of fit test with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data of the study fits a necessary condition distribution, a sufficient condition distribution, a necessary and sufficient condition distribution from a certain population. The sample size was sufficient enough in order for the chi-square approximation to be used. The hyper-geometric distribution has been used to test the one-sided significance of the causal relationship k .

Probability values $<.05$ (P-value) were considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed using MS Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Without HCMV IgG seropositivity, no smoking

Theorem 3.1 (WITHOUT HCMV IgG SEROPOSITIVITY, NO SMOKING).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis:

HCMV IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of smoking.

Alternative Hypothesis:

HCMV IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of smoking.

Proof by the study of Li et al. The study of Li et al. (see study of [Li et al., 2017](#)) provided some data (see table 2) on the relationship between HCMV positivity and smoking. The data are very convincing with respect to this relationship ($k = +0,013$; p (SINE) = 0,991; X^2 (SINE—Bt) = 0,127; X^2 (SINE—At) = 1,563; P Value (SINE)= 0,009). This data of (p (IOU) = 0,321) the study of Li et al. support the Null-hypothesis: without HCMV positivity, no smoking. □

3.2. Without HCMV IgG seropositivity no alcohol consumption

Theorem 3.2 (WITHOUT HCMV IgG SEROPOSITIVITY NO ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis:

HCMV IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of alcohol consumption.

Alternative Hypothesis:

HCMV IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of alcohol consumption.

Proof by the study of Li et al. The study of Li et al. (see study of [Li et al., 2017](#)) provided some data (see table 3 and table 4) on the relationship between HCMV positivity and alcohol consumption. Under conditions of a fair study design, Li et al. (see study of [Li et al., 2017](#)) were able to provide evidence (see table 4) that a HCMV infection is a necessary condition of alcohol consumption (p (SINE) = 0,9856115108; p Value (SINE)= 0,0142854696) while the causal relationship k is positive. In other words, **without a HCMV infection, no alcohol consumption**. Human alcohol consumption appears to be related to a HCMV infection. □

3.3. Without HCMV IgG seropositivity no EH

Theorem 3.3 (WITHOUT HUMAN CYTOMEGALOVIRUS IgG SEROPOSITIVITY NO ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION).

CLAIM. Null-Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of essential hypertension. Alternative Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Proof by the study of Li et al., 2011. Even under conditions of an unfair study design ($p(\text{IOU}) = +0,604810997$), Li et al. (see [Li et al., 2011](#)) were able to provide evidence (see table 5) that a HCMV infection is a necessary condition of essential hypertension ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,9621993127$; p Value (SINE) = 0,0370951591) while the causal relationship k is positive. In other words, **without a HCMV infection, no essential hypertension.** □

3.4. Without HCMV IgG seropositivity no EH

Theorem 3.4 (WITHOUT HUMAN CYTOMEGALOVIRUS IgG SEROPOSITIVITY NO ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Alternative Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Proof by the study of Vahdat et al., 2013. The study of Vahdat et al. (see study of [Vahdat et al., 2013](#)) has been able to provide evidence (see table 7) that a HCMV infection is a necessary condition of essential hypertension ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,9897377423$; p Value (SINE) = 0,0102097804) while the causal relationship k is positive. In other words, **without a HCMV infection, no essential hypertension.** □

3.5. Without HCMV IgG seropositivity no EH

Theorem 3.5 (WITHOUT HUMAN CYTOMEGALOVIRUS IgG SEROPOSITIVITY NO ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Alternative Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Proof by the study of Tang et al., 2014. The study of Tang et al. (see study of [Tang et al., 2014](#)) has been able to provide evidence (see table 8) that a HCMV infection is a necessary condition of essential hypertension ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,9897377423$; p Value (SINE) = 0,0102097804) while the causal relationship k is positive independently of an unfair study design ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0,53625$). In other words, **without a HCMV infection, no essential hypertension.** □

3.6. Without HCMV IgG seropositivity no EH

Theorem 3.6 (WITHOUT HUMAN CYTOMEGALOVIRUS IgG SEROPOSITIVITY NO ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Alternative Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Proof by the study of Jeong et al., 2016. The study design of the study of Jeong et al. (see study of [Jeong et al., 2016](#)) (see table 9) is biased ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0,786407767$). Furthermore, Jeong et al. (see study

of Jeong et al., 2016) did not present a control group. However, this had no effect on the calculation of the necessary condition relationship, because all patient with hypertension were HCMV positive. Based on this fact, the data were to some extent of use. The study of Jeong et al. (see study of Jeong et al., 2016) has been able to provide evidence (see table 9) that a HCMV infection is a necessary condition of essential hypertension (p (SINE) = 1,0; p Value (SINE)= 0,0) while the study design has been unfair (p (IOU)= 0,786407767). In other words, **without a HCMV infection, no essential hypertension**.

□

3.7. Without HCMV IgG seropositivity no EH

Theorem 3.7 (WITHOUT HUMAN CYTOMEGALOVIRUS IgG SEROPOSITIVITY NO ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Alternative Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Proof by the study of Li et al., 2017. The study design of the study of Li et al. (see Li et al., 2017) has been unfair (p (IOU)=0,632326821; see table 10). The data provided by Li et al. (see Li et al., 2017) are self-contradictory ($k < 0$). Nonetheless, the same data were of some, even if restricted, value. The study of Li et al. (see study of Li et al., 2017) has been able to provide evidence (see table 10) that a HCMV infection is a necessary condition of essential hypertension (p (SINE) = 0,9804618117; p Value (SINE)= 0,0193485549). However, the causal relationship has been $k < 0$ and the study design has been unfair (p (IOU)= 0,632326821). In other words, the hypothesis **without a HCMV infection, no essential hypertension** appears to be true even if the data of Li et al. (see study of Li et al., 2017) are only of restricted value.

□

3.8. Without HCMV IgG seropositivity no EH

Theorem 3.8 (WITHOUT HUMAN CYTOMEGALOVIRUS IgG SEROPOSITIVITY NO ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSION).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Alternative Hypothesis: HCMV IgG sero-positivity is not a necessary condition of essential hypertension.

Proof by the study of Feng et al., 2018. The study design of the study of Feng et al. (see Feng et al., 2018) has been unfair (p (IOU) = 0,45; see table 11). However, the data provided by Feng et al. are not self-contradictory ($k > 0$) and of some, even if restricted value. The study of Feng et al. (see Feng et al., 2018) has been able to provide evidence (see table 11) that a HCMV infection is a necessary condition of essential hypertension (p (SINE) = 0,9833333333; p Value (SINE)= 0,0165285462), the causal relationship has been $k > 0$ and the study design has been unfair (p (IOU)= 0,45). In other words, the hypothesis **without a HCMV infection, no essential hypertension** appears to be true.

□

4. Discussion

It is a bit brave to try to draw correct conclusions for a long time about the relationship between HCMV and EH given the contradictory data presented. So, silence on this matter is sometimes worth more than gold. To make matters worse, however, some studies had shown a quite impressive study design and were able to achieve amazing results. All things considered, it appears to be permissible, with some degree of certainty, to draw preliminary conclusions about the relationship between HCMV and EH while it remains an important investigational subject to define the role of HCMV in essential hypertension. This review may serve as a hypothesis generating approach which justifies a very systematical approach to this relationship. A radical turn will be needed to satisfy the unquenchable thirst for a satisfactory treatment of essential hypertension. This paper has the potential to lead to new treatments for essential hypertension directed at the antiviral therapy of HCMV or prevention by a vaccine against HCMV. Furthermore, there is some evidence the HCMV is responsible for alcohol consumption and for smoking too, with all the consequences which might develop. At this point, the point at issue isn't about who was first, 'either the chicken or the egg' but to find medical answers to serious medical problems. The foremost advantage of this study is the justified and reasonable assumption that HCMV seropositivity determines essential hypertension, smoking and alcohol consumption.

5. Conclusions

This study provides some strategic insights into the mechanisms of HCMV with essential hypertension. In conclusion, without HCMV seropositivity, no EH.

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6. Patient consent for publication

Not required.

Conflict of interest statement

No conflict of interest to declare.

Private note

This is only a working paper which is not peer-reviewed. Thus far, it was not possible to publish the content of this paper by a Web of Science, EBSCO, Scopus, PubMed/Medline et cetera indexed journal.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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^f<https://www.mendeley.com/search/?authorFullName=Ilija%20Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87&page=1&query=Barukcic&sortBy=relevance>

^g<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija-Barukcic-2>

^h<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87%22&sort=mostviewed>

ⁱ<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87,%20Conference%22>

^j<https://twitter.com/ilijabarukcic?lang=de>

^khttps://twitter.com/Causation_Journ

^lhttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^m<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukI00jpw8HTwg>

ⁿ<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>